

STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS REGARDING EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT AT PEOPLE'S NURSING SCHOOL - LUMHS JAMSHORO- AN APPLICATION OF DREEM MODEL

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Abstract

Background: The dundee ready educational environment measure (DREEM) is a widely used tool for assessing the educational environment in medical and nursing colleges. It captures students' views on learning, instructors, academic self-perception, and social interactions through 50 items. Therefore, assessing the academic environment is crucial for delivering a high-quality, student-focused curriculum, fostering critical thinking, collaboration, and mutual support. Evaluation encourages continuous improvement in nursing education, guiding the development of knowledge, skills, and ethics vital for personal and societal growth.

Methodology This research employed a descriptive cross-sectional study design. A stratified random sampling method was used to select 200 out of 412 using pre tested questionnaire consisting 50 items was distributed to the selected students. The data collected were analyzed through SPSS version 25 and Excel with the aimed to understand the perceptions of nursing and medical undergraduate students regarding their educational environment at PNS.

Results: Based on the DREEM data model, the study findings revealed that majority 58% of the participants were females, 60% are between 18 and 23 years old and 27% were from final years, the overall, students expressed satisfaction with their learning environment, engagement in institutional activities, and the curriculum. However, concerns were noted regarding teaching styles, clinical teaching, unclear support systems for stressed students were highlighted, and nearly half of the respondents reported feelings of fatigue and boredom due to over written work.

Conclusion and Recommendations: The study concluded that students generally hold more positive perceptions of their educational environment than negative ones. The majority of students expressed satisfaction based on their participation in the questionnaire. The findings shed light on various aspects of the education environment at PNS LUMHS Jamshoro and highlight areas where improvements can be made to enhance the overall learning experience.

INTRODUCTION**1. Background**

The educational environment, encompassing physical and social aspects, is vital for an effective education program as it enhances progress, skills, critical thinking, independence, intellectual well-being, and self-confidence of nursing students(1). The educational environment cultivates essential talents in nursing students, equipping them to tackle future challenges, achieve milestones, find enjoyment, and actively engage in their educational journey. There is a significant relationship between a superior extracurricular experience and the enhancement of students' cognitive skills, performance, and satisfaction((2). The educational environment includes the atmosphere within the classroom, department, or institution, comprising student perceptions of facilities, learning opportunities, teacher competence, faculty attitudes, and peer relationships(3).

The educational environment plays a crucial role in student learning and has a substantial impact on students' satisfaction with their course of study, perceived well-being, goals, and academic performance. The perceptions of students regarding their educational environment have been extensively investigated across various levels of the education system. With the growing emphasis on student-centered teaching and learning in health professions education, there has been a renewed interest in this area, particularly due to the recent focus on enhanced quality assessment monitoring(4).

In recent years, there has been an increasing emphasis on developing learning environments centered around students, highlighting the necessity for educational institutions to regularly evaluate and improve their academic atmosphere. Nursing students face a distinct set of academic and clinical challenges that influence their views on this environment. These perspectives can have a considerable effect on their mental health, engagement in their studies, and confidence in clinical settings. Ongoing evaluation aids in identifying areas that need enhancement, promoting an environment that supports comprehensive student growth and better learning results(5, 6).

The DREEM assessment system evaluates the quality of the educational setting in medical or nursing colleges. This approach takes into account students' perspectives on learning, teachers, the

environment, their academic self-image, and their social self-image(7). The DREEM tool includes 50 items related to teaching and learning in health professional colleges(8).

The DREEM was developed to assess the learning environment in medical schools and other healthcare institutions. It was designed by a group of international educators from medical schools and health professions through a Delphi process over ten years ago. The measure's validity was confirmed by testing with students from various countries. There are other evaluation tools available as well, including the medical education environment measure (MEEM), the postgraduate hospital educational environment measure (PHEEM), the surgical theatre educational environment measure (STEEM), and the anaesthetic theatre educational environment measure (ATEEM)(9, 10).

The DREEM tool consists of five subscales: students' perception of learning (SPL), students' perception of teachers (SPT), students' academic self-perception (SAP), students' perception of the atmosphere (SPA), and students' social self-perception (SSP), this widely recognized instrument has been used globally to assess the educational climate within healthcare institutions, offering valuable insights into student experiences and the effectiveness of pedagogical approaches(11).

The academic environment refers to all aspects of the learning environment, including the physical classroom, faculty members, and the college environment. It is a critical factor in student achievement and encompasses various elements such as physical infrastructure, social interactions, and intellectual stimulation, all of which significantly influence learning activities and outcomes(12). Efficient academic environments include well-equipped lecture rooms, educational resources, laboratories, and competent teachers, all of which have been shown to enhance student motivation, engagement, attentiveness, and academic performance(13). Assessment of the academic environment at each educational and medical site is essential for delivering a high-quality, student-focused curriculum. To conduct assessments across multiple sites, specialties, and student groups, it is crucial to utilize a comprehensive, legitimate, and dependable tool(14).

The learning environment that addresses both the internal and external needs of students is likely to lead to more positive and successful educational outcomes by promoting active engagement and learning. Establishing an effective learning environment in medical practice depends on various factors, including the student admission process, the quality of the teaching environment, and the active involvement of relevant stakeholders(15). An ideal educational environment should foster critical thinking, academic advancement, social interaction, collaboration, and mutual support among students. Furthermore, incorporating student feedback is crucial for improving the educational environment. Nursing education entails acquiring knowledge, skills, principles, beliefs, and habits that foster the growth of individuals who are well-rounded and morally responsible in personal and societal settings(16).

The evaluation of the learning environment in professional nursing institutions encourages continuous improvement and innovation. Nursing education provides a platform for nurses to develop discipline-specific knowledge and skills. Numerous studies have been conducted worldwide, including in Pakistan and other medical disciplines, to assess students' perceptions of the learning environment(17).

However, previous studies in Pakistan have mainly focused on other issues, which are insufficient to fully capture nursing students' perspectives on the learning environment. To ensure effective and meaningful learning experiences, it is necessary to establish a supportive environment that facilitates the teaching process, implements interventions, and enhances the overall educational atmosphere(18).

The learning environment in nursing significantly influences students' academic progress, actions, and overall well-being. In shaping a robust curriculum, the educational environment guides what and how nursing students study. While numerous medical and dental colleges in Pakistan have employed the DREEM tool, there have been noticeably fewer studies carried out in nursing schools. Therefore, this study aimed to investigate the perception and views on the educational environment at the Peoples Nursing School, Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshoro.

1.2 Rationale of Study:

The effectiveness of environmental education programs is crucial in determining the level of knowledge gained, motivation and learning outcomes. Nursing, as a profession, is facing the challenges posed by globalization and addressing them by forming global partnerships to exchange information and improve human health. The foundation for improving patient health and safety lies in the competency of healthcare providers, which is largely dependent on the education of nurses (WHO 2009). The academic environment encompasses the physical, intellectual, and emotional surroundings perceived by both students and teachers. These perspectives are based on three key components: the physical environment, the intellectual and emotional climate.

1.3 Study Aim

The study investigates students' perceptions of the educational environment at Peoples Nursing School, Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences in Jamshoro. It focuses on factors such as instruction quality, resource availability, peer interactions, and faculty support, aiming to understand their impact on students' academic experiences and personal development in nursing education.

1.4 Research Question

- What is students' perceptions concerning Educational Environment at People's Nursing School, LUMHS Jamshoro.

1.6 Study Objective

- i. The objective of this study was to investigate the perceptions of the education environment at the Peoples Nursing School (PNS) in Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshoro, utilizing the DREEM model.

METHODOLOGY

Study Setting

This research study was carried out at People's Nursing School, Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshoro.

Study Design

This study employed a descriptive cross-sectional design.

Period of study

Study was completed within six months after the approval of synopsis from REC committee, LUMHS Jamshoro. This period was deemed sufficient to complete all necessary phases of the research, including participant recruitment, data collection, and analysis.

Study population and Sample Size

This study included the entire population of students studying at PNS-LUMHS in Jamshoro during the data collection period. The estimated sample size for the study was calculated based on an estimated study population of 412 using Raosoft Software. The calculation was done with a margin of error of 5% (0.05) and a confidence level of 95%. As a result, the final sample size determined was 200.

Sampling technique

In this research, a simple stratified sampling method was employed to select the sample, ensuring that each member of the population had an equal opportunity to be included.

Inclusion criteria

Consenting undergraduate students of both genders currently studying in PNS-LUMHS, Jamshoro.

Exclusion criteria

Postgraduate students of PNS, students who did not want to reveal the information and who were absent during data collection.

Data collection tool

The Dundee Ready Education Environment Measure (DREEM) is a commonly used tool for evaluating the learning environment in various academic fields, especially in medicine and health sciences. The DREEM score is obtained from a 50-question survey, which is divided into two sections: Demographics and DREEM inventory questions.

Data Collection Method:

Data for this study were collected after receiving approval from the Research Ethics Committee (REC) of Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences in Jamshoro. A self-developed questionnaire was utilized to gather the data. Before participation, participants were given a comprehensive explanation of the study's objectives, their rights as participants, and were invited to ask any questions about the survey. Participation was entirely voluntary, and individuals were encouraged to join without any pressure. Enrollment of participants took place only after obtaining their written consent.

Data analysis

The research data was collected and managed in MS excel, and then it was analyzed through the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. To determine specific variables, frequency and percentage calculations were made, and graphs and pie Figures were utilized for visual representation.

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Ethical Research Committee (ERC) of LUMHS, and necessary permissions were granted by the Director of selected institution. Informed consent was secured from all participants, and the study adhered to the protocols established by the ERC of the selected institution.

RESULTS

The **table 1** displays the distribution of demographic data for 200 respondents. It includes 42% males and 58% females, indicating more female respondents. Age-wise, 60% are between 18 and 23 years old, while 40% are older than 23 years old. A significant 93% of respondents were unmarried, with only 7% married. In terms of education, fourth-year students make up 27%, followed by second-year students at 25%.

Table1: Demographic Data of the study participants

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	84	42
	Female	116	58
Age	18-23 years	120	60
	Above 23 years	80	40
Marital status	Unmarried	186	93

	Married	14	7
Year of education	First	48	24
	Second	50	25
	Third	48	24
	Fourth	54	27

Table 2 presents the first 25 items of the DREEM inventory, which reflect students' perceptions of various aspects of their educational experience, including learning, teaching quality, atmosphere, academic self-confidence, and social support. Therefore results indicates that students expressed a high level of confidence in their ability to pass, with 90% affirming this belief (Item 10). They also viewed their teachers as knowledgeable (90.5% for Item 2) and patient (75% for Item 6). The instruction was perceived as focused (84.5% for Item 20) and effective in boosting their confidence (89.5% for Item 22). On the social front, students reported having good friends (64% for Item 15) and enjoying a satisfactory social life (59% for Item 19). However, there were notable

areas of concern. Only about half of the students felt that the teaching approach was student-centered (49.5% for Item 13) or that it fostered their competence (49% for Item 16). A significant number also perceived the teaching style as authoritarian (52% for Item 9) and even ridiculing (35.5% for Item 8). Additionally, many students experienced stress-related fatigue (47.5% for Item 4) and reported average levels of support for managing stress (50.5% for Item 3). The atmosphere in both wards and lectures was described as lacking in relaxation, with only 27% (Item 11) and 44.5% (Item 23), respectively, noting a positive environment. Lastly, approximately 40% acknowledged that cheating was an ongoing issue (Item 17).

Table 2: shows frequency and percentage of DREEM Results (Items 1-25)

Item No.	Statement	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	I am encouraged to participate in class	119	59.5
2	The teachers are knowledgeable	181	90.5
3	There is a good support system for stress	101	50.5
4	I am too tired to enjoy the course	95	47.5
5	Learning strategies still work now	132	66
6	The teachers are patient with patients	150	75
7	The teaching is often stimulating	128	64
8	The teachers ridicule the students	71	35.5
9	The teachers are authoritarian	104	52
10	I am confident about passing this year	180	90
11	Atmosphere relaxed during ward teaching	54	27
12	The school is well timetabled	74	37
13	The teaching is student-centered	99	49.5
14	I rarely feel bored	96	48
15	I have good friends in this school	128	64
16	The teaching helps to develop competence	98	49
17	Cheating is a problem in this school	80	40
18	Teachers communicate well with patients	89	44.5
19	My social life is good	118	59
20	The teaching is well-focused	169	84.5
21	I am being well prepared for my profession	132	66
22	The teaching helps to develop my confidence	179	89.5
23	Atmosphere relaxed during lectures	89	44.5

24	The teaching time is put to good use	111	55.5
25	The teaching overemphasizes factual learning	101	50.5

Table 3 which covers items 26-50, continues to assess the exact five domains, with greater emphasis on clinical relevance, atmosphere, feedback, and social well-being.

The results indicated that students valued the opportunity to ask questions (Item 49: 80.5%) and felt inspired by the learning environment (Item 43: 75.5%). They recognized that teachers provided effective feedback (Item 29: 78.5%) and were well-prepared for their classes (Item 40: 74%). Students reported high levels of concentration (Item 36: 78%), noted that

seminars felt more relaxed than ward teaching (Item 34: 64%), and viewed accommodation options positively (Item 46: 66.5%). However, regarding area of concern, many students found the experience disappointing (43.9%) and felt there was insufficient constructive criticism from teachers (41%). Only half believed that long-term learning was emphasized (51%) or that the knowledge gained was relevant to their careers (50.8%). A large number noted that teaching was overly teacher-centered (71.5%) and focused too much on factual learning and rote memorization.

Table 3: shows frequency and percentage of DREEM Results (Items 26–50)

Item No.	Statement	Frequency	Percentage (%)
26	Last year’s work prepared me well	88	44
27	I am able to memorize all I need	102	51
28	I seldom feel lonely	104	52
29	Teachers provide feedback to students	157	78.5
30	Opportunities to develop interpersonal skills	114	57
31	I have learned a lot about empathy	106	53
32	Teachers provide constructive criticism	82	41
33	I feel comfortable in class socially	117	58.5
34	Atmosphere relaxed during seminars/tutorials	128	64
35	I find the experience disappointing	88	43.9
36	I am able to concentrate well	156	78
37	Teachers give clear examples	108	54
38	I am clear about learning objectives	113	56.3
39	Teachers get angry in class	107	53.5
40	Teachers are well prepared for classes	148	74
41	My problem-solving skills are being developed	112	55.8
42	Enjoyment outweighs stress	111	55.5
43	Atmosphere motivates me as a learner	151	75.5
44	The teaching encourages active learning	105	52.3
45	Learning is relevant to career in healthcare	101	50.8
46	My accommodation is pleasant	133	66.5
47	Long-term learning is emphasized	102	51
48	The teaching is too teacher-centered	143	71.5
49	I feel able to ask questions	161	80.5
50	The students irritate the teachers	52	26

The bar chart of DREEM subscales indicates that students generally perceive their educational

experience positively, but there are areas needing improvement:

Perception of Learning (64%): Students feel they are learning well, but improvements in teaching methods and resources are possible. Perception of Teachers (64.1%): While students view their teachers positively, further efforts are needed to ensure all feel fully supported. Academic Self-Perception (59.7%) A lower score suggests students may lack confidence in their academic abilities, highlighting the need for personalized feedback and support. Perception of Atmosphere

(58.2%) A somewhat neutral view of the learning environment suggests a need for a more engaging and supportive atmosphere. Social Self-Perception (55.2%) This lowest score indicates a lack of social integration, suggesting a need for improved peer interaction opportunities. However, there are positive perceptions overall, significant improvements are required, especially in social integration and the learning environment, to enhance student well-being and success.

DISCUSSION

For the current study, the use of DREEM for assessing the nursing students' perceptions regarding Educational Environment at People's Nursing School, LUMHS Jamshoro. In this study, the total population of PNS-LUMHS students in Jamshoro was around 412, and the researcher selected less than around 200 students from each batch. The DREEM questionnaire is a commonly used tool to evaluate learning environments in the field of medicine and health sciences across different educational settings.

The data shows the perceptions of various aspects of the learning environment, teachers, academic self-perceptions, atmosphere, and social self-perceptions of the students.

Perception of Learning (PoL):

The Perception of Learning (PoL) is a crucial aspect of the DREEM model, which refers to the individual's subjective perception of their learning experience in a particular educational setting, the results of current study shows that the majority of students (59.5%) feel encouraged to participate in class and are satisfied with the teaching methods used in the classes (73%). Furthermore,

students generally believe that the teaching is well-focused (84.5%) and helps to develop competence their learning objectives (85%). Regarding building confidence in students only 46.5% of respondents agree that the teaching helps to develop confidence. These findings comparison with existing literature indicates, this positive outlook on teaching methodologies and active participation contributes significantly to a constructive learning atmosphere(19).

Perception of Teachers (PoT):

In terms of (PoT), which measures students' perceptions of their learning environment in a particular academic setting. The PoT component specifically assesses students' perceptions of their teachers and their teaching methods. In this research study, most students are satisfied with the knowledge of their teachers (94.5%) and feel that the teachers are patient (75%) and have good communication skills (83.5%). This aligns with findings from other studies indicating that a supportive educational environment, characterized by effective teaching and opportunities for engagement, positively influences student perceptions of learning(20).

Academic Self-Perceptions (ASP):

This domain of the DREEM model measures students' beliefs about their own abilities and potential to perform well academically. Therefore this component of DREEM model assess students' level of confidence in their abilities and the extent to which they see themselves as capable of succeeding in their academic pursuits. By measuring students' self-perceptions, the statement "I am a good student," or "I am confident in my ability to do well in school." This study founds the majority of students feel confident about passing this year (91%) and feel well prepared for their profession (88.5%). However, only 45% of respondents feel that their previous learning strategies continue to work for them. According to previous studies(21, 22), offer significant insights on their overall well-being and academic success. Student trust in their knowledge significantly increased over the semester, with heightened confidence closely associated with actual knowledge gains.

Perceptions of Atmosphere (PoA):

This model measures students' perceptions of the overall atmosphere of their learning environment, includes factors such as the level of engagement, motivation, and support provided by teachers and classmates, as well as the quality of the physical environment, resources, and materials available to support learning. The findings of the current study revealed that the majority of students feel that the atmosphere is relaxed during lectures (69.6%) and there are opportunities to develop interpersonal skills (79.4%). In contrast, only 43.9% of students find the school experience disappointing. Conversely, previous research indicates that a substantial proportion of students perceive their learning environment as less than ideal, impacting their motivation and engagement(23). Such discrepancies highlight the critical need for continuous assessment of the educational environment, especially within the dynamic context of nursing education, to ensure alignment with student needs and pedagogical objectives(24). Further analysis of the DREEM subscales provides a more granular understanding of student perceptions, revealing specific strengths and weaknesses within the educational environment at People's Nursing School.

Social Self Perception (SSP):

SSP in the DREEM questionnaire refers to students' perceptions of their social self, such as their relationships with peers, teachers, and other people at their educational institution. Because the SSP scores can provide valuable information about the social climate of a learning environment and can help educators and administrators understand the extent to which students feel supported, engaged, and valued within their community(25). The results of current research indicates that, the most students feel that they have a good support system (50.8%) and a good social life (81.4%) at the school. However, 47.8% of respondents feel that they are too tired to enjoy the course. This aligns with prior research indicating that a positive educational environment, encompassing a supportive social milieu and manageable academic demands, significantly influences student satisfaction and academic outcomes(26). This observation highlights a potential area for intervention, as student fatigue can negatively impact academic performance and overall well-being, suggesting a need to explore curriculum load and student support mechanisms(27).

While the overall perception of atmosphere and social support is positive, the prevalence of fatigue suggests a need to investigate factors such as curriculum intensity, extracurricular demands, and access to wellness resources, which could mitigate student burnout and enhance their engagement with the course(28). Overall the majority of students have a positive perception of their learning experience, teachers support system, academic self perception, academic atmosphere, and social life at the selected settings..

5.2 Conclusion

This study concludes that the most students had positive perceptions of their educational environment across several domains. Perception of Learning, students felt encouraged to participate and satisfied with teaching methods, though there was a need to enhance their confidence. Perception of Teachers, students were generally pleased with teachers' knowledge and communication skills, but had concerns about potential negative behaviors from teachers. Academic Self-Perceptions, students felt confident about passing and being prepared for their professions, but needed improvement in learning

strategies. Perceptions of Atmosphere, a relaxed lecture environment was noted, though some students found their school experience disappointing. Social Self-Perception, students reported a supportive social life, but mentioned fatigue affecting their enjoyment of the course. Overall, while perceptions were mainly positive, areas for improvement included boosting confidence, addressing teacher behavior, enhancing learning strategies, and tackling student fatigue. These insights can help educational institutions improve the learning environment and student experience.

Recommendations

- **Enhancing Confidence-building Measures:** To address this, implement strategies like interactive discussions, group activities, and public speaking opportunities. Encourage constructive feedback and create a supportive environment to nurture self-esteem and belief in students' abilities.
- **Promoting Positive Teacher-Student Interactions:** Address student concerns about teachers mocking them and displaying authoritarian behavior by implementing training programs focused on respectful teacher-student relationships. Emphasize effective communication, empathy, and creating a positive, inclusive environment that encourages mutual respect and open expression among students.
- **Improving Timetabling and Resource Management:**
 - Consider reviewing the timetabling process to reduce conflicts and optimize resources. Allocate sufficient time for each activity to minimize stress. Involve students in the decision-making to identify areas for improvement.
 - **Strengthening Support Systems:**
 - Implement support mechanisms like counseling, peer networks, and stress management workshops to help students with academic and personal challenges. Promote awareness of these resources and encourage students to seek help when needed.

Authors Contributions

This work was a collaborative effort by all authors. The author JK Conceptualize the study. Data analysis and entered data in SPSS: IAC & JK JK conducted the data collection.

LM, IAC, and JK reviewed and edited the final draft of the manuscript.

All authors read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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